

COMPRESSION PROPERTIES OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL CFRP LAMINATES WITH EMBEDDED LITHIUM-ION POLYMER BATTERIES

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ABSTRACT

Multifunctional composites that combine high load-bearing properties and high electrical energy storage capacity have potential application in electric and hybrid vehicles. This paper presents an experimental study into the effect of embedding single or multiple lithium-ion polymer (LiPo) batteries on the mechanical and electrical responses of a carbon-epoxy laminate loaded in compression. The results indicate that embedding batteries has a significant adverse effect on compression properties. The property reductions are attributed to several factors, including the compressive properties of the battery being much lower than the composite material, geometric stress concentration induced by the battery, discontinuities in the carbon fibres in the load-bearing direction, and the soft polymer layer at the battery-composite interface affecting load transfer. The results show that multiple embedded batteries stacked vertically in the compression load direction is the most desirable configuration. This configuration resulted in smaller reductions to the compressive properties compared to the horizontal side-to-side battery configuration. The electrical performance of the embedded LiPo battery was not affected significantly by the compression loading, even when plastically deformed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural weight reduction is an approach being pursued by the automotive industry to achieve reductions in fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. To achieve this objective, carbon fibre composites are increasingly being used in structural applications. In addition, electric propulsion continues to grow in popularity with increasing numbers of electrical and hybrid motor vehicles appearing on the market. These vehicles have relatively high electric energy storage requirements, which has significant implications on empty vehicle weight. One approach to improve the structural and energy storage efficiencies is to utilise multifunctional composite components. This concept involves integrating energy storage devices within composite structures, so they also become load-bearing [1, 2]. There is growing interest in embedding batteries within vehicle components to provide the dual functions of load-bearing and energy storage. In particular, the integration of batteries into composite materials to create light-weight, energy storage structures is a promising approach for next-generation hybrid and electric vehicles.

The application of multifunctional composite laminates with embedded LiPo batteries in structural and semi-structural applications requires an understanding of their mechanical properties. Numerous studies have investigated the mechanical and dynamic properties as well as the energy storage capacity of fibre-polymer laminates containing embedded batteries [3-5]. Thomas et al. [6] investigated the electrical and mechanical performance of multifunctional laminates with embedded LiPo battery cells.

The batteries increased both the bending stiffness and failure load of the laminate. The energy storage capacity of the multifunctional laminates ranged between 40 to 60 Wh/L. Other studies have shown that embedding batteries in the core of sandwich composites has an adverse effect on the in-plane (edgewise) compression properties and, to a lesser extent, tensile properties [7]. The effect of embedded batteries on the in-plane compression properties of composite laminates is yet to be addressed. Compression properties are critical for many engineering applications, including automotive structures.

The aim of this study is to experimentally investigate the effect of embedded LiPo batteries on the compression properties and failure modes of a carbon-epoxy laminate, which is used in selected automotive components for light-weighting. In this study, we investigate the influence of the number and orientation of embedded batteries on the response of the composite to compression loads. The effect of compressive loading on the electrical performance and physical integrity of the embedded batteries is also investigated. LiPo batteries were selected for this study because of their high energy density, ability to sustain non-periodic charging, and high charge-discharge rates [8]. For these reasons, LiPo batteries are a popular choice for energy storage in hybrid and electric vehicles.

2 MATERIALS & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Composite Materials and Batteries

The laminate in this study were made using plain woven T300 carbon fabric with an areal density of 200 g/m² (AC220127 supplied by Colan Ltd.) and a low-temperature cure bisphenol-A based epoxy resin (105/206 supplied by West System). The laminate contained 24 stacked plies of the carbon fabric, and the LiPo batteries (500 mAh, 3.7 V) were inserted into rectangular-shaped cut-outs made in the central 18 plies (Fig. 1a). Three plies of fabric without cut-outs were applied to the upper and lower surfaces to completely enclose the batteries within the preform (Fig. 1b). The fabric preform was then infused with the liquid epoxy resin at room temperature using the vacuum bag resin infusion (VBRI) process. No heat or excessive pressure was applied during the VBRI process to avoid damage to the batteries, and the laminate was cured at room temperature. Laminate specimens were fabricated without batteries, with one battery (Fig. 2a) and two batteries arranged in two different arrangements: vertical and horizontal (Figs. 2b and 2c). The specimen dimensions were 150 mm long, 100 mm wide and 6 mm thick. The mechanical properties of the cured CFRP laminates and the LiPo battery are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: (a) Carbon fabric with an embedded LiPo battery prior to VBRI fabrication. (b) X-ray CT image of cross-section view of the cured laminate showing an embedded battery. Note that the white horizontal band is an artefact of the X-ray imaging and not a physical feature in the laminate.

Figure 2: Schematic (front view) of the CFRP laminates showing the distribution of embedded LiPo batteries for (a) one battery, (b) two batteries – arranged vertically, (c) two batteries – arranged horizontally. All dimensions in mm. The compression load direction is indicated.

Property	CFRP [9]	LiPo battery [10]
Density, ρ	1,550 kg/m ³	2,080 kg/m ³
Young's Modulus, E	45 GPa	150 MPa
Compression strength, σ	300 MPa	1.0 MPa
Shear modulus, G	3.9 GPa	300 MPa
Shear strength, τ	42 MPa	35 MPa

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the CFRP laminate and LiPo battery.

The LiPo batteries used in this study are manufactured and supplied by the LiPol Battery Co. Ltd. Each battery had a nominal weight of 10 grams, measured 40 mm long, 30 mm wide and 4 mm thick. The batteries were enclosed within a thin aluminium pouch and the minimum and maximum nominal discharge voltage of the batteries was 2.7 V and 4.2 V, respectively. Insulated copper wiring was soldered to the end tabs of the batteries using 60/40 lead tin solder. This enabled electrical testing of individual batteries within the laminate.

2.2 Compression test methods

In-plane compression tests were performed on laminate specimens with and without batteries using the fixture and procedure described in ASTM D7137 [11]. The test fixture employs anti-buckling guides to avoid structural buckling and ensuring material failure within the gauge region. The specimens were compressively loaded at an end-shortening rate of 0.5 mm/min until failure using a 250 kN MTS loading machine.

Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was used to measure the strain fields in the vertical direction (ϵ_{yy}) at the outer surface of the laminates during testing. To enable DIC, a high contrast random speckle pattern was applied to the surface before testing. A digital camera was positioned a short distance from the specimen, and DIC images were taken every 10 seconds over the course of each test until failure. Post-processing of the images to extract the displacement and strain fields was performed in MATLAB using the procedure described in [12]. The DIC analysis allowed for the strain measurements to be averaged over the entire sample gauge section to determine the global strain, which was used to calculate the compression modulus. Five specimens of each laminate specimen type were tested.

2.3 Battery tests

The electrical performance of the LiPo batteries embedded within the laminates was monitored before, during and after the compression tests. Cyclic charge-discharge tests were performed using a Cellpro PowerLab 6 multi-chemistry battery workstation. The measurements were taken at a constant 1C rate (500 mAh^{-1}) at room temperature. During cycling, the voltage, current, internal resistance and capacity of the batteries was measured at ten second intervals. Each battery tested was cycled three times in total, and therefore any change in performance can be attributed to damage caused solely by the compression loading, rather than by ageing effects that can occur with LiPo batteries.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Compression properties of composites laminates with embedded batteries

Compression stress-strain curves for the laminates with and without batteries are shown in Fig. 3. The corresponding compression properties are given in Table 2. Note that the gradient of the curve in Fig. 3 defines the apparent compression modulus of the laminates. The apparent modulus of the laminates was reduced by the presence of one or two batteries. The laminate with multiple embedded batteries arranged horizontally exhibited the greatest reduction in modulus. The curves for the laminate reached a maximum load, which defines the ultimate strength, and this was also reduced significantly by the batteries. The laminates with multiple batteries arranged horizontally exhibited the greatest reduction in strength. In contrast, the laminates with multiple batteries arranged vertically exhibited similar property reductions to the laminate with one embedded battery.

Figure 3: Compression stress-strain curves of the laminates with and without batteries. The strain values represent the global average of the laminate specimen.

No. embedded batteries	Compression strength (MPa)	Compression modulus (GPa)
0	293 ± 13	41.5 ± 1.3
1	166 ± 12	34.0 ± 1.4
2 (vertical)	168 ± 8	30.4 ± 1.5
2 (horizontal)	98 ± 12	23.7 ± 1.5

Table 2: Compression properties of the laminates.

The reductions to the compressive properties of the laminate caused by the batteries can be attributed to several factors. These include compressive properties of the battery being much lower than those of the composite material, geometric stress concentration caused by the battery, discontinuities in the carbon fibres in the load-bearing direction and the soft polymer layer at the battery-composite interface which limits to load transfer efficiency between the two materials.

The modulus and failure stress of the LiPo battery is much lower than the carbon-epoxy laminate (see Table 1). Removing carbon fibres from the laminate to create space to internally store the batteries therefore lowers the stiffness and strength in the load-bearing direction. Placing two batteries vertically lead to the same property reductions as a single battery, and this is because the cross-sectional load-bearing area of laminate material is the same in both configurations. However, when two batteries are located side-by-side in the horizontal direction then a larger amount of load-bearing laminate material is removed, resulting in the greater reductions to the modulus and failure stress.

The battery also caused a geometric stress concentration within the laminate due to its elastic properties being much lower than the carbon-epoxy material. For example, the stress concentrations in the laminates with embedded batteries are evident in the DIC results in Fig. 4, which show magnified strains (ϵ_{yy}) at the battery locations. Failure of the laminates with embedded batteries initiated at the high strain regions (Fig. 5a) and propagated along the width of the laminate until final failure as shown in Fig. 5b. Laminates without embedded batteries failed catastrophically across the width of the gauge section as shown in Fig. 5b.

Figure 4: Vertical strain (ϵ_{yy}) maps measured at 0.3% bulk strain for the (a) control laminate without batteries and laminates with (b) one, (c) two (vertical) and (d) two horizontal batteries. The locations of the batteries are indicated.

Figure 5: Damage progression observed during compression testing for laminate specimens with single and multiple embedded batteries. (a) Crack initiation and (b) final catastrophic failure for a specimen with two embedded batteries arranged vertically.

3.2 Battery performance in composite laminates under compression

Electrical measurements of the LiPo battery were taken prior to compression testing, in-situ during testing and after the laminates had failed. In-situ measurements were taken at 30% and 60% of the predetermined failure stress. Fig. 6 shows the voltage charge/discharge, capacity and internal resistance of the batteries at the measurement points. Despite the small increases in the internal resistance, the charge/discharge capacity of the battery was not changed significantly under compression loading, even when the laminate had failed. This reveals that the application of high compression forces, do not adversely affect the charge/discharge performance of the type of LiPo battery used in this study.

Figure 6: (a) Charging and discharging cycles, (b) capacity and (c) internal resistance measured before, during and after compression testing. Charge-discharge cycles performed during static compression testing were conducted at 30% and 60% of the failure stress.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Embedding LiPo batteries inside carbon-epoxy laminates has a significant adverse effect on the compression properties. The inclusion of one or more batteries had a large detrimental effect on the both the compression strength and modulus. The property reductions can be attributed to reduced load-bearing material, geometric stress concentrations within the material, discontinuities in the carbon fibres in the load-bearing direction, and the soft polymer layer at the battery-composite interface. The stress concentrations caused by the embedded batteries was confirmed via DIC analysis which showed magnified compressive strains at the locations of the embedded batteries. When using multiple batteries, the vertical alignment in the compression load direction causes a smaller reduction to the mechanical properties than when arranged side-by-side in the horizontal direction. The internal resistance, capacity and voltage charge/discharge properties of the LiPo battery were not significantly altered by compression loading. The battery is remarkably damage tolerant and was able to retain its electrical performance after failure of the laminate material.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L.E. Asp, E.S. Greenhalgh, Structural power composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **101**, 2014, pp. 41-61.
- [2] J.F. Snyder, E.L. Wong, C.W. Hubbard, Evaluation of commercially available carbon fibers, fabrics, and papers for potential use in multifunctional energy storage applications, *Journal of the Electrochemical Society*, **156**, 2009, pp. 215-224.
- [3] J. Galos, A.A. Khatibi, A.P. Mouritz, Vibration and acoustic properties of composites with embedded lithium-ion polymer batteries, *Composite Structures*, **220**, 2019, pp. 677-86.
- [4] T. Pereira, Z. Guo, S. Nieh, J. Arias, H.T. Hahn, Energy storage structural composites: a review, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **43**, 2009, pp. 549-60.
- [5] J.P. Thomas, M.A. Qidwai, Mechanical design and performance of composite multifunctional materials, *Acta Materialia*, **52**, 2004, pp. 2155-64.
- [6] J.P. Thomas, M.A. Qidwai, W. Pogue, G. Pham, Multifunctional structure-battery composites for marine systems, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **47**, 2013, pp. 5-26.
- [7] S. Shalouf, J. Zhang, C. Wang. Effects of mechanical deformation on electric performance of rechargeable batteries embedded in load carrying composite structures, *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, **43**, 2014, pp. 98-104.
- [8] A. Barré, B. Deguilhem, S. Grolleau, M. Gérard, F. Suard, D. Riu, A review on lithium-ion battery ageing mechanisms and estimations for automotive applications, *Journal of Power Sources*, **241**, 2013, pp. 680-9.
- [9] R.B. Ladani, A.R. Ravindran, S. Wu, K. Pingkarawat, A.J. Kinloch, A.P. Mouritz, Multi-scale toughening of fibre composites using carbon nanofibres and z-pins, *Composites Science and Technology*, **131**, 2016, pp. 98-109.
- [10] E. Sahraei, R. Hill, T. Wierzbicki, Calibration and finite element simulation of pouch lithium-ion batteries for mechanical integrity, *Journal of Power Sources*, **201**, 2012, pp. 307-21.
- [11] ASTM D7137 / D7137M-17: Standard Test Method for Compressive Residual Strength Properties of Damaged Polymer Matrix Composite Plates, West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International, 2017.
- [12] E. Jones, *Documentation for Matlab-based DIC code*, University of Illinois, 2015.